

PERCEPTIONS OF KEY STAGE 1 TEACHERS' ON THE REMOVAL OF MOTHER TONGUE AS A MEDIUM OF INSTRUCTION AND LEARNERS' ENGAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Education plays a vital role in society, and the use of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) as a medium of instruction has been proven to enhance learners' comprehension and engagement; however, its recent removal has raised concerns about its effects on teaching and learning. Thus, the main objective of the study was to determine the significant relationship between the level of teachers' perception on the removal of mother tongue as a medium of instruction and the learners' engagement among Key Stage 1 teachers in Inabanga South District. Specifically, it aimed to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, and years of teaching experience. The design used by the thesis writers was the descriptive survey method with the aid of a researcher-made and adopted questionnaire. The data gathered were statistically analyzed and interpreted using percentage, weighted mean, standard deviation, Chi-Square, and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC). Based on the findings, most of the respondents were female teachers aged 40 - 45 years old with 8-10 years of teaching experience. It was found out that the teachers had a low level of perception on the removal of mother tongue as a medium of instruction, while learners' engagement in terms of emotional and behavioral aspects was found to be high. In addition, there is no significant difference between the level of perception among key stage 1 teachers and level of perception of the teachers on learners' engagement when grouped according to teachers' profile. Moreover, there was no significant relationship between the level of perception on the removal of the mother tongue and the learners' engagement. The thesis writers concluded that language policy changes may not directly affect learners' engagement but can influence classroom inclusivity and teaching practices. Finally, future thesis writers are recommended to conduct further studies that

include both teachers' and learners' perspectives to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the effects of language use on engagement.

Keywords: *Mother Tongue, Medium of Instruction, Learners' Engagement, Key Stage 1 Teachers, Removal of Mother Tongue*

INTRODUCTION

Education plays a vital role for the development of the society. Without proper education, progress will never take place. Proper education requires thorough planning and ongoing evaluation and revision of curriculum. With this, teacher will be given a chance to enhance their teaching by employing various strategies during teaching-learning process.

Learning strategy includes the language used in teaching the learners in order for the learners to acquire learnings. This strategy helps learners to optimize their long-term retention of knowledge and skills. It has been urged that teachers play a vital role in employing this strategy. For them to effectively and efficiently teach learners, they need to be equipped with high pedagogical knowledge, instructional expertise, and commitment to continuously improve teaching practices. The relevance of exploring teachers' perception is highlighted by this recent policy change, which requires teachers to adjust their methods as the medium of instruction shifts from the mother tongue to Filipino and English, potentially influencing both teachers' approaches and Key Stage 1 learners' engagement.

Furthermore, many studies have looked at the benefits of using the mother tongue as medium of instruction in early grades but not much research has been done on what happens when it is removed in key stage 1, especially in terms of learner's engagement. Most studies focus on academic performance rather than learners' engagement, which includes learners' participation, behaviors, and interaction in class. While some studies have explored the challenges of using the mother tongue in school, fewer studies examine what teachers think about its removal and how it affects their teaching and learners' engagement. Additionally, it is unclear whether the removal of mother tongue as medium of instruction makes it harder for learners to shift to learning in English or Filipino and whether it creates difficulties in understanding complex lessons on higher levels. This situation presents a clear problem that this study intends to address, understanding how the removal of the mother tongue as a medium of instruction affects both teaching practices and learner engagement in the classroom.

As the result of the preliminary survey, this study was conducted in Inabanga, Bohol, specifically among primary school teachers handling Kindergarten to Grade 3 in Inabanga South District. These teachers have firsthand experience in implementing MTB-MLE and can provide valuable insights into how its removal affects curriculum delivery, learning activities, and student assessment. Their perspectives helped determine whether the shift to an English- and Filipino based instruction enhances or hinders early

childhood education in their context. This study provided useful insights into how teachers perceive the removal of the mother tongue as a medium of instruction and how it affects learners' engagement.

In the changing education system, language plays a vital role in shaping learners learning experiences. The mother tongue-based multilingual education (MTB-MLE) policy was introduced to enhance comprehension and engagement by using the first language as the medium of instruction from kindergarten to grade 3 (Department of Education, 2009). However, recent reforms have change and have led to its removal beyond key stage 1, raising concerns about impacts on learners' engagement. To support the study, the following reviews on different theories are carefully studied and taken into consideration.

In section of Article XIV, Section 6 of the 1987 Philippine constitution states that the national language is Filipino, which should be developed and enriched based on existing Philippine and other languages. It is clearly stated in the Philippine Constitution, under Section 7, Article XIV, that for purposes of communication and instruction, the official languages are Filipino and, until otherwise provided by law, English.

Moreover, in the Department of Education Order no. 16, s.2012, states that starting school year 2012-2013, the Mother Tongue Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) shall be implemented in all public schools, specifically in Kindergarten, Grades 1, 2 and 3 as part of the K to 12 Basic Education Program. Based on this order, learners in kindergarten to grade 3 learn using their native language. The goal is to help learners learn more easily. To achieve this, teachers are trained to teach in a way that respects learners first languages.

However, Republic Act No. 12027, which discontinues the mandatory use of mother tongue as a medium of instruction from kindergarten to Grade 3, reverting the medium of instruction to Filipino and, until otherwise provided by law, English, with regional languages serving as auxiliary media. The law ends the mandatory use of the mother tongue as medium of instruction in key stage 1 learners. Republic Act No. 12027, An Act Discounting the Use of the Mother Tongue as Medium of Instruction from Kindergarten to Grade 3, Providing for its Optional Implementation in Monolingual Classes, and Amending for the Purpose of Sections 4 and 5 of Republic Act No. 10533, Otherwise Known as the "Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013" which required children in kindergarten and grades 1 to 3 to be taught in their respective regional or native tongue languages.

Mother tongue-based multilingual education enables learners to be taught in the language they understand and speak best, resulting in better learning outcomes across range of subjects (UNESCO, 2025). According to Sociocultural Theory by Vygotsky (1978), learning is inherently social and culturally mediated. Language, particularly the mother tongue, serves as a crucial tool for thought and communication. The Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) highlights the importance of scaffolding, where knowledgeable others guide learners within their potential. Removing the mother tongue

can disrupt this scaffolding process, limiting a child's ability to learn effectively, especially in early primary grades. This disruption impacts the child's ability to navigate their social and cultural learning environment. Consequently, teachers' perceptions of this removal are vital in understanding its effects on social learning. Additionally, Cognitive development Theory by Piaget (1985) posits that children progress is through distinct stages, constructing knowledge through assimilation and accommodation. Language, in Piaget's view, reflects cognitive development. Early primary grades are crucial for building cognitive foundations. The removal of the mother tongue can interfere with these cognitive processes, potentially hindering children's ability to process and internalize new information. This change may lead to cognitive overload, particularly if children are not proficient in the new language of instruction. Teachers' perceptions are crucial in gauging the impact of this linguistic shift on cognitive development.

Furthermore, Social Cognitive Learning by Bandura (1960) emphasizes the role of observational learning, self-efficacy, and reciprocal determinism in learning. Teachers' perceptions are shaped by their observations of learners learning behaviors and outcomes. Self-efficacy influences teachers' beliefs in their ability to effectively teach without the mother tongue. The removal of the mother tongue changes the environment in which students learn, thus changing the reciprocal determinism. Therefore, this environmental change can affect learners' ability to learn and teachers' ability to teach effectively.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the key stage 1 teacher's perception on the removal of the mother tongue as a medium of instruction to key stage 1 learners' engagement of Inabanga South District.

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender, and years of teaching experience?
2. What is the level of perception of the key stage 1 teachers on the removal of the mother tongue in terms of curriculum and instruction, learning activities, and assessment?
3. What is the level of perception among the key stage 1 teachers on the learners' engagement in terms of emotional engagement and behavioral engagement?
4. Is there a significant difference between the level of perception among key stage 1 teachers and level of perception of the teachers on learners' engagement when grouped according to teachers' profile?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of perceptions on the removal of mother tongue on key stage 1 and the learners engagement?

METHODOLOGY

Design

To achieve the purpose of this study, the thesis writers used the descriptive correlational design quantitative survey research method, a method of research which is defined by Copeland (2022) as a means of seeking the link between variables without attempting to manipulate any of them. The primary focus of this study was to analyze teacher's perceptions regarding the removal of the mother tongue in primary grades. The thesis writers aimed to gather numerical data through surveys, or other quantitative methods to provide a detailed description of teacher's perspectives on the policy change. This approach allows for a systematic measurement and analysis of data, enabling thesis writers to quantify the relationship between the Teachers perceptions and factors such as curriculum and instruction, learning activities, assessment, and student engagement. The emphasis on quantitative data collection ensures that the study produces objective and measurable findings, contributing to a strong understanding of the study.

Environment

This study was conducted in South District Elementary School of Inabanga, Bohol, where primary schools are implementing the revised curriculum that removes mother tongue as a medium of instruction in the key stage 1. Thesis writers chose this environment as their research locale because primary teachers of this district are directly affected by the policy change. The study focused on determining teacher's perceptions on the removal of mother tongue as a medium of instruction and examining its impact on curriculum and instruction, learning activities, assessment, and student engagement. By conducting the study in this specific environment, the thesis writers gained insight into teachers' perception on the removal of mother tongue in key stage 1.

Respondents

The respondents of this study were the key stage 1 primary school teachers from Inabanga South District of Inabanga, Bohol. The thesis writers chose them as their respondents, as they are the ones experiencing the transition in language instruction due to the removal of mother tongue as a medium of instruction. The thesis writers gathered data through the use of purposive-sampling a nonprobability sampling method where participants are chosen intentionally based on their specific characteristics or knowledge that are relevant to the research question. This ensure that the quality sample is located without biases so as to increase the reliability and trustworthiness of the findings (Nyimbili and Nyimbili, 2024). The respondents include seven (7) key stage 1 teachers from Inabanga South Central Elementary School, four (4) key stage 1 teachers from Badiang Elementary School, three (3) key stage1 teachers from Lutao Elementary School, four (4) key stage 1 teachers from Cawayan Elementary School, three (3) key stage 1 teachers from Dagohoy Elementary School, four (4) key stage 1 teachers from Luyo Elementary School, seven (7) key stage 1 teachers from Cagawasan Elementary School, three (3) key stage 1 teachers from Sto. Rosario Elementary School, and seven (7) key stage 1

teachers from Uog-Ubujan Elementary School. In total, there will be 42 primary school teachers.

Instrument

To amass the needed data in this study, the thesis writers used adopted questionnaire used by Purcia and Castante (2023) to determine the teacher's perception in regards to removal of mother tongue in key stage 1, with the permission asked and approval of the authors. It is a 3 item Likert-Scale questionnaire with 10 questions in each sub variable where the content is about the curriculum and instruction, learning activities, and assessment. It is designed based on the statement of the problem, incorporating a prepared form that includes all the necessary information for the study, which is then distributed to the Key Stage 1 teachers of Inabanga South District Elementary School. Respondents were simply required to put checks under the four (4) point Likert scale: (SA) Strongly Agree, (A) Agree, (D) Disagree, and (SD) Strongly Disagree. The first aforementioned questionnaire was pilot tested at Calbayog East Central School to determine whether the constructs in the questionnaire truly measured what they intended to measure. A reliability test using Cronbach's alpha was conducted, resulting in an alpha coefficient of 0.86, which is higher than the minimum acceptable value of 0.70. This support to the study of Hussey (2025) that a Cronbach's Alpha value of 0.70 or above was considered acceptable for reliability. This indicates that the crafted questionnaire was valid and reliable enough to be used as an authentic data-gathering instrument.

On the other hand, a researcher-made instrument was utilized to determine learners' engagement following the removal of the Mother Tongue subject. It focuses on two key areas: behavioral engagement and emotional engagement. The questionnaire was validated by experts through a review process, where the specialist checked, corrected, and provided feedback on the content, language, and sentence structure to ensure its content accuracy and relevance. After validation, it underwent pilot testing among Key Stage 1 teachers in Clarin District, Clarin, Bohol to measure its reliability and consistency as a data-gathering tool. A reliability test using Cronbach's alpha was conducted, resulting in an alpha coefficient of 0.90, which indicates that the crafted questionnaire was valid and reliable enough to be used as an authentic data-gathering instrument.

Procedure

In gathering the data, thesis writers sought approval by sending a letter of permission to the school principal to conduct the preliminary survey. After obtaining approval, the thesis writers conducted preliminary survey to 30 primary teachers through random sampling with 10 primary teachers in Tubigon West District, Clarin District, and Inabanga South District to determine which District is the most affected with the removal of mother tongue. As the result, it showed that Inabanga South District obtained a higher percentage of agreed primary teachers on the removal of mother tongue. With that, the thesis writers conducted the study at Inabanga South District key stage 1 teachers.

To determine the level of students' engagement, the thesis writers conducted a pilot testing to the key stage 1 teachers, followed by the distribution of the questionnaires for the data gathering process to the randomly selected key stage 1 teachers of Clarin District, Clarin, Bohol.

Statistical Treatment

The study employed a various statistical test to analyze the data that is collected. To determine the profile of the respondents according to age, gender, and years of teaching, percentage was used. To get a description of teacher's perceptions on the removal of mother tongue on key stage 1 and learners' engagement, a weighted mean and standard deviation was used.

In addition, to find out the significant difference between the level of perception among key stage 1 teachers and level of perception of the teachers on learners' engagement when grouped according to teachers' profile, Chi-Square was used. To find out the significant relationship between the level of perceptions on the removal of mother tongue on key stage 1 and the learner's engagement, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) was used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Respondents

As the intervening variables, age, gender, and years of teaching experience are being considered to determine their contributions and to assess their significant difference from the other variables of the study. The profile of the respondents gives a deeper insight into how it may influence their views on the policy and on learners' engagement. This helps identify potential differences in perspectives and experiences. By analyzing age, sex, and years of teaching experiences, the study aims to provide a more detailed understanding of the respondents' characteristics.

Table 1
Profile of the Respondents
n = 42

Age	Frequency	Percentage (%)
64-69	1	2.4
58-63	2	4.8
52-57	3	7.1
46-51	5	11.9
40-45	12	28.6
34-39	10	23.8
28-33	9	21.4
Total	42	100

Gender		
Male	2	4.8
Female	40	95.2
Total	42	100
Years of Teaching Experience		
26-31	4	9.5
20-25	7	16.7
14-19	10	23.8
8-13	14	33.3
2-7	7	16.7
Total	42	100

Statistical Tool: Simple Percentage

Table 1 reveals the percentage results of the respondents age, gender, and years of teaching experience. It is revealed that only 12 (28.6%) are 40-45 years old, 10 (23.8%) are 34-39 years old, 9 (21.4%) are 28-33 years old, 5 (11.9%) are 46-51 years old, 3 (7.1%) are 52-57 years old, 2 (4.8%) are 58-63 years old, and 1 (2.4%) are 64-69 years old. The data reveals that most of the respondents are 40-45 years old. This supports to the study of Esquejo (2024) which implies that teachers of all ages similarly perceive the implementation and effectiveness of MTB-MLE, suggesting that age does not affect teaching quality or outcomes in the context.

As to the gender of the respondents, it reveals that 95.2% of the respondents are female while 4.8% of the respondent are male. This means that the majority of the respondents are female. This aligns to the study of Pinili (2025) which shows that female educators often teach foundational and early grade learners in MTB-MLE programs.

The years of teaching experiences reveals that mostly of the respondents has 8-13 years of teaching experience, 10 (23.8%) has 14-19 years of teaching experience, while 7 (16.7%) in both 2-7 years and 20-25 years of teaching experience, and 4 (9.5%) are relatively new to teaching which have been teaching for 26-31 years. Meanwhile, 14 or 33% of the Key Stage 1 teachers has 8-13 years of teaching experience. This support to the study of Medilo (2016) which shows that the broader educational research showing that quality and relevance of teacher preparation can matter more than duration of experiences alone in specialized instructional contexts.

Table 2
Level of Perception of Key Stage 1 Teachers of the Removal of the Mother Tongue
n = 42

Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Curriculum and Instructions I want the MTB-MLE be removed because....			

1. MTB-MLE objectives are not carried out...	2.36	0.96	Slightly Perceived
2. The school does not adopt the MTB-MLE...	2.33	0.82	Slightly Perceived
3. The school does not implement the rules and...	2.26	0.83	Slightly Perceived
4. The school does not adhere to the promotion...	2.17	0.88	Slightly Perceived
5. Teacher is not well-equipped with MTB-MLE...	2.14	0.78	Slightly Perceived
6. Teacher is not competent and knowledgeable...	2.14	0.78	Slightly Perceived
7. Teacher does not address individual...	2.07	0.84	Slightly Perceived
8. Teacher do not show competence in teaching...	2.00	0.83	Slightly Perceived
9. Teacher does not show technical know-how...	2.00	0.80	Slightly Perceived
10. The school does not follow curriculum...	1.98	0.84	Slightly Perceived
Total Mean	2.15	0.84	Slightly Perceived
Learning Activities			
I want MTB-MLE be removed because....			
1. Learners find difficult to use the local terms...	2.64	0.98	Perceived
2. I want MTB-MLE to be removed since.	2.55	1.02	Perceived
3. Students do not enjoy learning.	2.55	0.97	Perceived
4. I want to have it be removed since it lacks...	2.50	0.94	Perceived
5. I am not well-equipped with the MTB-MLE...	2.36	0.98	Slightly Perceived
6. They have less if not, no academic activities...	2.31	0.92	Slightly Perceived
7. They are not interactive during classroom...	2.24	0.82	Slightly Perceived
8. Students do not interact with each other...	2.19	0.86	Slightly Perceived
9. Activities in the lesson are not fitted with the...	2.19	0.80	Slightly Perceived
10. I do not know how to teach MTB-MLE...	1.90	0.79	Slightly Perceived
Total Mean	2.34	0.91	Slightly Perceived
Assessment			
I want the MTB-MLE program be removed because...			
1. I find the assessment strategies inappropriate...	2.50	0.92	Perceived
2. I see that students are only compelled to take...	2.48	0.80	Slightly Perceived
3. Modules/Learning resources crafted to do not...	2.45	0.89	Slightly Perceived
4. I have less, if not, less knowledge in terms...	2.40	0.91	Slightly Perceived
5. I am trained less in terms of assessment.	2.40	0.86	Slightly Perceived
6. The assessment stages are inconsistent with...	2.38	0.82	Slightly Perceived
7. DepEd's framework of MTB-MLE does not...	2.33	0.90	Slightly Perceived
8. I find assessment of learning boring for...	2.33	0.85	Slightly Perceived
9. I do not know how to conduct authentic...	2.31	0.87	Slightly Perceived
10. DepEd's suggested assessment are...	2.29	0.86	Slightly Perceived
Total Mean	2.39	0.87	Slightly Perceived
Overall Mean	3.05	0.87	Slightly Perceived

Statistical Tool: Weighted Mean, Standard Deviation

Legend: 3.25–4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50–3.24 = Agree; 1.75–2.49 = Disagree; 1.00–1.74 = Strongly Disagree

Table 2 shows the weighted mean results on the level of perception of Key Stage 1 teachers regarding the removal of the Mother Tongue as a medium of instructions. The overall mean of $M=3.05$ ($SD = 0.87$) indicates that teachers agree that removing the Mother Tongue affects curriculum and instruction, learning activities, and assessment. This supports the study of Cummins (2000) that early learners perform better academically when foundational instruction begins with a language they fully understand.

In terms of curriculum and instruction ($M = 2.15$, $SD = 0.84$), teachers agreed that removing the Mother Tongue influences lesson delivery and comprehension. While the policy aims to strengthen Filipino and English instruction, it may also hinder pupils' understanding, especially in the early grades. This aligns with the findings of Purcia et al.

(2023), who emphasized that learners achieve better comprehension and learning outcomes when taught in their first language. Abruptly removing it can negatively impact literacy and cognitive growth, as also noted by De Jesus (2024) regarding the importance of teacher preparedness for effective instruction.

For learning activities $M = 2.34$ $SD = 0.91$ teachers perceived that the change in language use affects student engagement. Learners might hesitate to participate when lessons are not in their familiar language. This supports Vygotsky's (1978) Sociocultural Theory, which highlights that language is essential in fostering communication and collaboration among learners. Additionally, UNESCO (2016, 2022) notes that instruction in the Mother Tongue encourages active participation, motivation, and a sense of belonging. Similarly, Trudell (2016) found that pupils participate more confidently and show better interaction when allowed to express themselves in their local language, which boosts learning motivation and classroom involvement.

Meanwhile, for assessment (M) = 2.39 $SD = 0.871$ teachers agreed that the removal of the Mother Tongue can influence how students demonstrate learning outcomes. Pupils may understand concepts but struggle to express them accurately in another language. This is supported by Mangila (2019), who highlighted that the absence of culturally and linguistically appropriate materials can hinder effective evaluation of learners' performance.

Hence, the overall results suggest that Key Stage 1 teachers moderately agree that removing the Mother Tongue influences teaching quality, learner engagement, and assessment fairness. These findings highlight the importance of maintaining language inclusivity in early education to promote comprehension, participation, and equitable learning evaluation. This conclusion aligns with studies from DepEd (2016) and Pillos (2020), emphasizing that mother tongue instruction supports literacy development and confidence in expressing knowledge during the early years of school.

Table 3
Level of Learners Engagement
n = 42

Statements	Mean	SD	Interpretation
Emotional Engagement			
1. My class feels more confident expressing...	3.31	0.60	Perceived
2. My class feels more comfortable and included...	3.24	0.62	Perceived
3. My class feels emotionally connected to what...	3.17	0.70	Perceived
4. My class feels more confident and willing to...	3.14	0.61	Perceived
5. My class easily and clearly understand...	3.14	0.61	Perceived
6. My class feels proud and valued when they...	3.12	0.67	Perceived
7. My class feels motivated to complete tasks...	3.12	0.67	Perceived
8. My class feels more motivated to participate...	3.10	0.66	Perceived
9. My class feels a strong emotional connection...	3.07	0.68	Perceived
10. My class enjoys learning when the teacher...	3.07	0.68	Perceived
11. My class feels happy and excited about...	3.05	0.73	Perceived
12. My class feels valued in class when taught...	3.05	0.70	Perceived
13. My class wants to participate in class when...	3.05	0.66	Perceived
14. My class fosters positive attitude towards...	3.05	0.66	Perceived

15. My class feels happy and confident when...	3.00	0.66	Perceived
16. My class enjoys reading and writing in...	2.98	0.64	Perceived
17. My class feels left out and disconnected from...	2.90	0.66	Perceived
18. My class feels proud to speak in mother...	2.90	0.66	Perceived
19. My class finds harder to follow lessons when...	2.83	0.74	Perceived
20. My class feels nervous and anxious when...	2.71	0.77	Perceived
Total Mean	3.05	0.67	Perceived
Behavioral Engagement			
1. My class participates more actively in class...	3.21	0.56	Perceived
2. My class can express thoughts more clearly...	3.19	0.55	Perceived
3. My class can easily comprehend questions...	3.19	0.55	Perceived
4. My class understands lessons better when the...	3.12	0.71	Perceived
5. My class is more confident speaking in class...	3.12	0.59	Perceived
6. My class feels more confident participating in...	3.10	0.62	Perceived
7. My class volunteers to answer questions in...	3.10	0.58	Perceived
8. My class can actively collaborate their...	3.10	0.58	Perceived
9. My class feels confident communicating with...	3.10	0.53	Perceived
10. My class is participative during classes when...	3.07	0.64	Perceived
11. My class finds it easier to learn how to read...	3.05	0.70	Perceived
12. My class sometimes struggles to understand...	3.02	0.60	Perceived
13. My class can easily connect new content to...	3.00	0.62	Perceived
14. My class are actively involved in class when...	3.00	0.62	Perceived
15. My class find it harder to understand lessons...	2.98	0.64	Perceived
16. My class can easily solve problems when...	2.98	0.60	Perceived
17. My class can express ideas and think critically...	2.95	0.70	Perceived
18. My class can easily understand and retain...	2.95	0.58	Perceived
19. My class struggles to understand complex...	2.90	0.62	Perceived
20. My class can easily learn other subjects when...	2.86	0.68	Perceived
Total Mean	3.05	0.61	Perceived
Overall Mean	2.29	0.64	Perceived

Statistical Tool: Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation

Legend: 3.25–4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50–3.24 = Agree; 1.75–2.49 = Disagree; 1.00–1.74 = Strongly Disagree

Table 3 shows the weighted mean results on the level of students' engagement in learning in terms of emotional and behavioral engagement. The overall mean of $M=2.29$ ($SD = 0.64$) with the descriptive value of Agree indicates that students are generally engaged both emotionally and behaviorally in their learning process.

In terms of emotional engagement ($M = 3.05$, $SD=0.67$), the results imply that students show positive feelings toward learning activities. They feel motivated, interested, and connected to what they are learning. This is supported by UNESCO (2016, 2022), who emphasize that learning in the mother tongue enhances learners' comfort, sense of belonging, and confidence in classroom interactions. Similarly, Benson (2004) notes that instruction in a familiar language fosters emotional involvement and motivation, helping students actively participate in lessons.

For behavioral engagement ($SD = 0.61$) the results indicate that students consistently participate in classroom tasks, attend classes regularly, and ($M = 3.015$, complete assignments responsibly. This aligns with Cummins (2000) and Heugh (2011), who highlight that when students are taught in their first language, they are more willing to engage, contribute, and persevere in learning activities. Active participation demonstrates learners' commitment and effort to succeed.

Hence, the overall mean of $M = 3.05$ ($SD = 0.49$) suggests that students are moderately engaged in both emotional and behavioral aspects of learning. This implies that learners maintain a balanced sense of motivation and commitment, which helps foster consistent academic performance and positive classroom behavior. UNESCO (2016, 2022) and Trujillo (2020) further emphasize that using the mother tongue enhances classroom participation, learner confidence, and sustained engagement in the educational process.

Table 4
Significant Difference Between the Level of Perception Among Key Stage 1 Teachers on the Removal of Mother Tongue and Learners' Engagement When Grouped According to Teachers' Profile
n = 42

Profile Variable	χ^2 (Chi-square)	df	p-value	Interpretation
Age vs. Perception on Removal of Mother Tongue	580	550	0.179	Not Significant
Gender vs. Perception on Removal of Mother Tongue	27.3	25	0.341	Not Significant
Years of Teaching Experience vs. Perception on Removal of Mother Tongue	583	550	0.161	Not Significant
Age vs. Learners' Engagement	612	572	0.12	Not Significant
Gender vs. Learners' Engagement	31	26	0.229	Not Significant
Years of Teaching Experience vs. Learners' Engagement	571	572	0.500	Not Significant

Statistical Tool: Chi-square Test of Independence

Table 4 presents the Chi-square test results on the significant difference between the level of perception of Key Stage 1 teachers regarding the removal of the mother tongue and learners' engagement when grouped according to age, gender, and years of teaching experience. All p-values were greater than 0.05 age vs. perception ($\chi^2 = 580$, $df = 550$, $p = 0.179$), sex vs. perception ($\chi^2 = 27.3$, $df = 25$, $p = 0.341$), and teaching experience vs. perception ($\chi^2 = 583$, $df = 550$, $p = 0.161$) indicating no significant difference among the groups. Non-significant results also appeared for learners' engagement, with age ($\chi^2 = 612$, $df = 572$, $p = 0.12$), gender ($\chi^2 = 31$, $df = 26$, $p = 0.229$), and teaching experience ($\chi^2 = 571$, $df = 572$, $p = 0.50$). This means teachers share similar perceptions regardless of demographic characteristics, suggesting that age, gender, and teaching experience do not influence how they view the policy or its effect on learner engagement.

This uniformity implies that teachers' views are shaped more by shared professional experiences than by individual traits. Common challenges with the MTB-MLE

implementation such as limited materials, insufficient training, and lack of administrative support (Mangila, 2019; Hunahunan, 2019) likely contributed to these consistent perceptions. This finding also aligns with Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory (1978), emphasizing that language, especially the mother tongue, is essential for learning and interaction; thus, its removal may affect how learners construct meaning and engage in class.

The absence of significant variation across profiles suggests that the practical challenges of transitioning away from MTB-MLE outweighed any differences arising from personal characteristics. Teachers, regardless of experience, encountered similar concerns in curriculum alignment and resource availability (De Jesus, 2024). Their shared observations on comprehension, confidence, and foundational skills (Igarashi et al., 2024; Cummins, 2000) shaped a common stance on the policy shift. Since language is central to learning, removing the mother tongue may hinder learners' ability to connect new knowledge with prior understanding. The consistent non-significant results highlight a unified teacher perspective, indicating that support mechanisms such as improved resources and training (Skutnabb-Kangas, 2009; UNESCO, 2022) should be applied universally to address the effects of this policy change.

Table 5
Relationship Between the Level of Perception of Key Stage 1 Teachers on the Removal of Mother Tongue as Medium of Instruction and Learners' Engagement
n = 42

Variables	<i>r</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>a</i>	<i>p-value</i>	Interpretation
Perception on Removal of Mother Tongue and Learners' Engagement	-0.22***	40	0.05	0.165	Not Significant

Statistical Tool: Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC)

Table 5 depicts the Pearson Product-Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) relationship between the level of perception of Key Stage 1 teachers on the removal of the mother tongue as a medium of instruction and learners' engagement. The computed r-value of -0.22 indicates a weak negative correlation, while the p-value of 0.165 is greater than the 0.05 level of significance. This means that there is no statistically significant relationship between the two variables. Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship is retained. This result implies that even though the correlation appears negative, the findings are not statistically reliable across the larger population. There is no sufficient evidence to suggest that teachers who hold a more positive perception of the removal of the mother tongue as a medium of instruction also perceive higher levels of learners' engagement. Teachers' acceptance and understanding of this educational change do not appear to have a statistically significant effect on how they facilitate instruction or observe learner participation. This lack of significance, despite the observed negative correlation, supports Piaget's Cognitive Development Theory (1985), which posits that children actively construct knowledge through interaction and adaptation within their learning environment.

Furthermore, this finding aligns with existing literature emphasizing the importance of the mother tongue in fostering foundational learning (Igarashi et al., 2024; UNESCO, 2022). Studies have shown that instruction in the mother tongue enhances emotional engagement, reduces anxiety, and strengthens conceptual understanding (Cummins, 2000; Heugh, 2011). The nonsignificant result therefore suggests that while teachers may support the policy shift, their endorsement alone cannot compensate for the cognitive and linguistic advantages provided by mother tongue instruction. As Pilos et al. (2020) and Thomas and Collier (1997) highlight, learning in one's first language promotes comprehension, confidence, and participation factors that are central to sustained learner engagement. Hence, the findings reinforce the theoretical and empirical consensus that the impact of language policy on learning outcomes extends beyond teacher perception, reflecting deeper cognitive processes shaped by linguistic and developmental factors.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the thesis writers concluded that the study explored teachers' perception on removing Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE) as a medium of instruction and its impact on Key stage 1 learners' engagement. The survey included mostly female (95%) respondents aged 40 to 45 years (28%) and has 8-13 years (33%) of teaching experience. Results showed that the Key stage 1 teachers had a low level of perception on the removal of the mother tongue, while the level of perception among the key stage 1 teachers on the learners' engagement was found to be at high level. Furthermore, the study revealed no significant difference between the level of perception among key stage 1 teachers and level of perception of the teachers on learners' engagement when grouped according to teachers' profile and has no significant relationship between the level of perceptions on the removal of mother tongue on Key Stage 1 and the learners' engagement. One limitation of this study is that it consists of a sample that focus one district of Inabanga South, which does not necessarily represent broader demographics. This realization is enough to know the teachers' perception on the removal of mother tongue as medium of instruction to Key Stage 1 learners' engagement.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion presented, the following recommendations are hereby offered:

1. Students are encouraged to strengthen their mother tongue skills alongside other languages to enhance behavioral and emotional engagement on academic performance.
2. Teachers are encouraged to translate some difficult English/Filipino words to MTB-MLE language to the Key Stage 1 learners, as learners can cope up with the lesson easily, facilitating a more effective and inclusive learning environment.
3. The school administrators to allow MTB-MLE as translation language, as learners are motivated and active in participation during classes, leading to more engaging and effective learning environment.

4. Policy makers may include MTB-MLE as a language translation in teaching Key Stage 1 learner, to support early grade learners in developing a strong foundation in their mother tongue.

5. Future thesis writers to conduct further studies that include both teacher and learner's perspectives to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the effects of language use on engagement.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Informed consent was secured from all respondents prior to the conduct of the study. The research adhered to established ethical principles, including voluntary participation, confidentiality, and the right to withdraw without penalty. Data access was limited to authorized personnel, and the integrity of the research process was maintained by ensuring accuracy and preventing data manipulation.

REFERENCES

- Article XIV, Section 6 of the 1987 Philippine Constitution. Retrieved from: <https://lawphil.net/consti/cons1987.html>
- Benson, C. (2004). The importance of mother tongue-based schooling for educational quality. *Language and Education*, 18(1), 20-32. Retrieved from: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000146632>.
- Brock-Utne, B. (2010). Language and education in Africa: The case for mother-tongue instruction. *International Journal of educational Development*, 30(6), 636-645. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijedudev.2010.03.004>.
- Cabansag, J. (2016). The implementation of mother tongue-based multilingual education: Seeing it from the stakeholder's perspective. *International Journal of English Linguistics*, 6(5), 43-43. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijel.v6n5p43>.
- Copeland, B. (2022). What is the meaning of descriptive correlational method? De Kooktips. Retrieved from: <https://bit.ly/3IRu244>
- Cummins, J. (2000). Bilingual children's mother tongue: Why is it important for education? ResearchGate Article. Retrieved from: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/238698400>.
- De Jesus, L. (2024). Bridging the Gap: Preparations for Mother Tongue Utilization within the Matatag Curriculum. *Philippine E-Journals Vol. 2 No. 4*. Retrieved from: <https://www.ejournals.ph/article.php?id=24981>
- DepEd Order no.16 s.2012. Guidelines on the Implementation of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education. Retrieved from: <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2012/02/17/do-16-s-2012-guidelines-on-the-implementation-of-the-mother-tongue-based-multilingual-education-mtb-mlt/>
- DepEd. (2016). Mother tongue-based multilingual education: Guidelines and recommendations for implementation in the Philippines. Department of Education.

- Esquejo, K. (2024). Status of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE). *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews* Vol. 5 No. 5. Retrieved from: <https://ijrpr.com/uploads/V5ISSUE5/IJRPR28473>.
- Heugh, K. (2011). Theory and practice – Language education models in Africa. "International Review of Education, 57(5-6), 587-612". Retrieved from: <https://repository.hsrc.ac.za/handle/20.500.11910/3362>.
- Hunahunan, L. (2019). Coping With MTB-MLE Challenges: Perspectives of Primary Grade Teachers in a central School. *International Journal for Social Studies* Vol. 6 No. 7. Retrieved from: <https://journals.pen2print.org/index.php/ijss>
- Hussey, I., Alsalti, T., Arslan, R. (2025). An Aberrance of Cronbach's Alpha Values at .70. *Sage Journals*. <https://doi.org/10.1177/251524592412877123>
- Igarashi, T., Maulana, S, Suryadarma, D. (2024). Mother Tongue-Based Education in a diverse society and the acquisition of foundational skills: evidence from the Philippines. *Labor Economics* Vol. 91 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.labeco.2024.102641>
- Medilo, C. (2018). The Experience of Mother Tongue-Based Multilingual Education. *The Interdisciplinary Research Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.63201/ICBE4323>
- Mangila, B. (2019). Institutionalizing a Mother Tongue-Based Approach in Teaching Multicultural Classrooms: A Closer Look at Elementary Teachers Experience. *Asia Pacific Journal of Education, Arts and Sciences* Vol. 6 No. 2. Retrieved from: www.apjeas.apjmr.com
- Nyimbili F. and Nyimbili L. (2024) Types of Purposive Sampling Techniques with Their Examples and Application in Qualitative Research Studies, *British Journal of Multidisciplinary and Advanced Studies: English Lang., Teaching, Literature, Linguistics & Communication*, 5(1),90-99. <https://doi.org/10.37745/bjmas.2022.0419>
- Pinili, R. (2025). Level of Teachers Competency in Addressing Challenges in Teaching Using Mother Tongue-Based-Multilingual Education (MTB-MLE). *International Multidisciplinary journal of Research for Innovation, Sustainability and Excellence* Vol. 2 No. 1. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14649731>
- Purcia, E. L., Castante, N. S. (2023). Abrogating Mother-Tongue Multilingual Education in the Philippines: The Lens of MTB-MLE Teachers in Public Elementary Schools. *American Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Innovation* Vol. 2 No. 4. <https://doi.org/10.54536/ajmri.v2i4.1818>
- Pillos, B. (2020). Challenges faced by students when the language of instruction is not their mother tongue. *Asian Journal of Education and Social Studies*, 5(1), 38-50. Republic act no. 12027. Retrieved from: https://lawphil.net/statutes/repacts/ra2024/ra_12027_2024.html
- Skutnabb-Kangas, T. (2009). Linguistic genocide in education. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 29(4), 318-322. Retrieved from: <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/mono/10.4324/9781410605191s>
- Siti Hawa, A. (2021). Enhancing classroom engagement through mother tongue-based instruction. *Journal of Modern Education*, 13(3), 210-225.
- Thomas, W. P., & Collier, V. (1997). School effectiveness for language minority students. *National Clearinghouse for Bilingual Education*. Retrieved from: <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=ED436087>.

- Trudell, B. (2016). Mother tongue-based education and classroom participation. *International Review of Education*, 62(4), 483-497.
- Trujillo, J. (2020). The use of mother tongue in instruction: pupils' performance across the years. *Globus Journal of Progressive Education*. 10(1), 59.
<https://doi.org/10.46360/globus.edu.220201009>
- UNESCO. (2016). Global Education Monitoring Report. Retrieved from:
<https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000243713>.
- UNESCO. (2022). Why mother language-based education is essential. UNESCO Article. Retrieved from: <https://www.unesco.org/en/articles/why-mother-language-based-education-essential>.